

**MALINA EGINIDA O'RGIMCHAKKANAGA (*TETRANYCHUS URTICAE* KOCH.)
QARSHI BIOPREPARATLARNI BIOLOGIK SAMARADORLIGI****¹Boltaev Botir Safarovich, ²Yusupova Muxlisa Shuxrat qizi**¹Toshkent davlat Agrar universiteti, q.x.f.n., dosent²Toshkent davlat Agrar universiteti, magistrant<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8357908>

Annotatsiya. Maqolada Toshkent viloyati sharoitida yetishtiriladigan malina ekinlarida uchraydigan o'rgimchakkanaga qarshi kurash tadbirlari va ularga qarshi biopreparatlarni qo'llash samaradorligi o'rganildi.

Kalit so'zlar: malina, o'rgimchakkana, biopreparat, zararkunanda, suyuqlik.

Аннотация. В статье изучены меры борьбы с паутиным клещом, обнаруженным на посевах малины, выращиваемых в условиях Ташкентской области, и эффективность применения против них биопрепаратов.

Abstract. In the article, measures to combat the spider mite found in raspberry crops grown in the conditions of Tashkent region and the effectiveness of using biopreparations against them were studied.

Keywords: raspberry, spider mite, biopesticide.

Kirish: Malina (*Rubus idaeus* L.) mashhur rezavor meva bo'lib, salomatlik uchun koni foyda, mevalari bolalar uchun parhez stolida va dorivor maqsadida qo'llaniladi. Shu bilan birga, ularning muhim oziq moddalari tananing to'g'ri ishlashi uchun qimmatli manba hisoblanadi.[1–4] Konsentrlangan meva sharbatlari, siroplar, muzlatilgan ovqatlar yoki murabbo ishlab chiqarishda ulardan foydalaniladi.[3] Bu o'simliklarning hatto barglari ham ichimliklar ishlab chiqarishda ishlatiladi.[5]

Ishlab chiqarish jarayonida ular doimo ko'plab zamburug'li kasalliklarga duchor bo'lishadi [6–8] va ko'p sonli zararkunandalar ularga zarar yetkazishi mumkin. [8–10]. Turli xil patogenlar va zararli hashoratlar bilan zararlangan mahsulotlarda meva sifati tushib ketadi, hattoki oziq-ovqat tarkibidagi yeyilmaydigan moddalar manbaiga aylantiradi.[11] Malina mevalariga kasallik va zararkunanda tushishini oldini olish uchun hosil bosqichida maxsus himoya choralarini qilish kerak bo'ladi. Ko'pincha bu kimyoviy moddalar pestitsidlar yordamida amalga oshiriladi (fugitsidlar, insektitsidlar va gerbitsidlar).[7,8,12,13]

Ushbu kimyoviy moddalardan intensiv foydalanish paytida tavsiya etilgan dozadan oshib ketgan holatlarda malina mevalari tarkibida ko'plab qoldiq moddalar bo'lishiga olib keladi. Bundan tashqari, bog'bonlar ko'pincha o'simliklarni himoya qilish vositalarini maqsadsiz foydalanishadi. Bu zararli bo'lgan qoldiqlar iste'molchi salomatligiga salbiy ta'sir qiladi.[13–15]

Mavjud pestitsidlardan foydalanishdan voz kechish va pestitsidlarisiz meva ishlab chiqarishga bo'lgan talabning ortishi malina va qoraqarag'at ekinlarida o'simliklarni himoya qilishning kelajakdagi yo'nalishini belgilab beruvchi kuchli tashqi bosim sifatida qaraladi.

Hozigi davrda oziq - ovqat xavfsizligi nuqtai nazaridan o'simliklarni zararkunanda va kasalliklariga qarshi qo'llaniladigan pestitsidlar o'rnini biopestitsidlarga almashtirilmoqda.

Biopestitsidlar-tabiiy materiallardan (hayvonlar, o'simliklar, mikroorganizmlar, ayrim minerallar) olingan pestitsidlar[2]. An'anaviy pestitsidlarning alternativi sifatida biopestitsidlar qishloq xo'jaligining umumiy ifloslanishini kamaytirishi mumkin, chunki ular bilan ishlash

xavfsiz, odatda foydali umurtqasizlar yoki umurtqali hayvonlarga kuchli ta'sir qilmaydi va parchalanishga qisqa vaqt talab qiladi[2].

O'zbekistonda keng tarqalgan malina (*Rubus*) ning zararkunandalaridan o'rgimchakkana (*Tetranychus urticae Koch.*) ning zarari sezilarli darajada.

(*Tetranychus urticae Koch*, Acari: Tetranychidae) to'g'ridan-to'g'ri oziqlanib, barglarda fotosintezning buzilishiga olib keladi [9].

Kuchli zararlanish natijasida avgustgacha barglar qurib qolishi mumkin. Barglarning erta qurib qolishi oqibatida sovuqqa chidamlilik uchun zarur bo'lgan fotosintetik zaxiralar yo'qoladi [14]. Kuzda zararlanish keyingi qishda kurtaklarning omon qolishini kamaytirishi mumkin [17].

Biotoksibatsillin, P (BTB) (BA-1500 EA/mg) biopreparatning asosini Bt subsp. thuringiensis tashkil qiladi. Tarkibida spora va endotoksindan tashqari suvda eruvchi β -ekzotoksin ham mavjud. Thuringiensis Inert qo'shimcha moddalari preparatning saqlanishini, namlanishini, tarqalishini va barqarorligini ta'minlaydi.

Diagramma 1. Akademik Mahmud Mirzayev nomidagi bog'dorchilik, uzumchilik va vinochilik ilmiy -tadqiqot institutidagi malina tajriba maydonidagi o'rimchakkananing rivojlanish dinamikasi.(2022-2023-y)

Biotoksibatsillin tarkibida kristalli oqsil mavjudligi ta'sirning ichak xarakterini aniqlaydi. Preparat hasharotlar tanasiga kirib, ichak funksiyasining buzilishiga olib keladi, buning natijasida ovqatlanish davri kamayadi. Beta-ekzotoksin hasharotlar tanasiga ichak va teri orqali kirib, hasharotlar hujayralarida RNK sintezini ingibirlyadi.

Malinada o'rgimchakkanasiga qarshi Bitoksibatsillin P biopreparatining 5 kg/ga sarf miqdorda sinovdan o'tkazilganda, Andoza variantida Vertimayk 20% sus.k. 0,05 l/ga sarf miqdorda olindi. Nazorat variantida esa ishlov berilmadi. Preparatlarni qo'l purkagich yordamida ishchi suyuqligi 400 l/ga sarf-me'yorda qo'llanildi. Tadqiqotlarimiz natijasiga ko'ra malina bog'larida o'rgimchakkanaga Bitoksibatsillin P biopreparati 5,0 kg/ga sarf miqdorida qo'llanilgan variantda

3 hisob kunida nazoratga nisbatan 56,8% samaradorlikka erishilgan bo'lsa, 14 hisob kuniga kelib esa bu ko'rsatgich 76,8% gacha etdi.

Andoza variant sifatida Vertimayk 20% sus.k. 0,05 l/ga sarf-me'yorda qo'llanilgan variantda 3 hisob kunida nazoratga nisbatan 80,7% samaradorlikka erishilgan bo'lsa, 14 hisob kuniga kelib esa bu ko'rsatkich 85,8% namoyon etdi.

Jadval-1.

Malina o'rgimchakkanasiga qarshi biopreparatlarning biologik samaradorligi.

(Toshkent viloyati, Toshkent tumani Akademik M.Mirzaev nomidagi BU va VITI ilmiy tajriba stansiyasi 2023 y.)

t/r	Variantlar	Preparatning lotincha nomi	Prep. sarf miqd, l/kg/ga	5 ta bargdagi zararkunandalarning o'rtacha soni, dona			Biologik samaradorlik, %					
				Dori sepilguncha	Dori sepilgandan keyin, kun.		3	7	14	3	7	14
					3	7						
1.	Nazorat	-	-	17,2	19,8	22,5	23,6	-	-	-		
2.	Vertimayk 20% sus.k	Abamectin	0,05	20,5	4,5	3,5	4,0	80,7	87,0	85,8		
3.	Bitoksibatsillin P n.kuk	Bacillus thuringiensis var.thuringiensis, БА-1500 EA/МГ	5,0	18,5	9,2	7,8	5,9	56,8	67,7	76,8		

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